
Annual report 2024
National Strategy for Data Management based
on the FAIR principles

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Terminologi/akronym	Beskrivelse
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AAAI	Authentication, Authorization and Accounting Infrastructure
AU	Aarhus Universitet
AAU	Aalborg Universitet
CBS	Copenhagen Business School
CISO Forum	Chief Information Security Officer Forum
CSC	IT Center for Science (Finland)
DAM	Digital Asset Management
DANS	Data Archiving and Networked Services
DeiC	Danish e-Infrastructure Consortium
DFF	Danmarks Frie Forskningsfond
DMP	Data Management Plan
DSL	Data Science Labs
DTU	Danmarks Tekniske Universitet
EU	European Union
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EUPD	The Energy Technology Development and Demonstration Programme
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GEUS	De Nationale Geologiske Undersøgelser for Danmark og Grønland
GFF	Grundforskningsfonden
GUPD	Grønt Udviklings- og Demonstrationsprogram
IAM	Identity and Access Management
IFD	Innovationsfonden Danmark
INSPIRE	(INfrastructure for SPatial InfoRmation in Europe)
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ITU	IT Universitetet
JISC	Joint Information Systems Committee (Storbritannien)
KU	Københavns Universitet
MUPD	Miljøteknisk Udviklings- og Demonstrationsprogram
NCC	National Competence Center
NFDI	National Research Data Infrastructure
OS	Open Science
PID	Persistent Identifier
RUC	Roskilde Universitet
SDU	Syddansk Universitet
T&I	Trust & Identity
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
URIS	Udvalget om Retningslinjer for Internationalt forsknings- og innovationssamarbejde
WAYF	Where Are You From

1. Executive summary from the FAIR Reference group

The 2024 Annual Report presents contributions from the six working groups of the FAIR Reference Group, each reporting on their respective focus areas for implementing the *National Strategy for Data Management based on the FAIR Principles*. Some working groups have provided specific recommendations and considerations, while others have focused on developing methods to address these areas in 2025.

This annual report provides a snapshot of the working groups' current progress and preliminary conclusions. It is to be emphasized that the contributions here represent the working groups' perspectives and recommendations, which will evolve over the coming years.

The report highlights the need for a substantially strengthened and more competent research support in data management (FAIRification) and for implementing data management policies at universities. Further inquiry is needed to determine whether a national competence center could beneficially support this; this will be a priority for the work in 2025. Furthermore, developments internationally, within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), and the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) will be monitored.

DeiC Dataverse, DeiC Storage, and Sensitive Storage are mentioned in the report as infrastructure solutions expected to promote FAIR practices in Denmark, thus implementation and rollout is critical. A future assessment of universities' use of these services is recommended. Likewise, potential solutions for the long-term preservation of research data will be an important area to follow in 2025, with data valuation playing a central role in this discussion.

Collaboration between research funders and universities is described as productive. Working group C notes that applications for data management support are typically approved by funders, but that this support is often embedded within the costs allocated for postdocs responsible for developing the project's data management. FAIR data management is rarely explicitly mentioned in applications, suggesting low awareness of the concept. Improved communication and dissemination between the parties, particularly regarding data management funding frameworks, would further promote FAIR practices.

Pertaining to security, working group E has established a constructive dialogue with key stakeholders, such as the CISO Forum (*Chief Information Security Officer Forum*) and the Ministry of Higher Education and Science. This collaboration provides a comprehensive overview of the many ongoing security initiatives, in light of the current geopolitical context.

Finally, the FAIR Reference Group hopes for a positive and constructive response from the stakeholders with whom the working groups engage, as they assess progress in implementation of the strategy.

2. Introduction

The National Strategy for Data Management based on the FAIR principles is now in its second mandate period, which extends until the end of 2025. The mandate for this period¹ has been formulated in such a way that it builds upon the conclusions and recommendations from the reporting of the last mandate period², as well as international developments concerning FAIR initiatives and practices.

In this mandated period, six working groups are participating in the strategy work:

- *A: Policies, tools and research support for FAIR data management*
- *B: Establishing FAIR infrastructure and long term preservation*
- *C: Financial plan for FAIR data*
- *D: Plan for structuring and developing FAIR competencies and knowledge*
- *E: Security aspects of FAIR data collaboration*
- *F: Valuation of data*

The implementation of FAIR in practice is an interdisciplinary effort involving several different professional areas. Implementation of the FAIR principles at public research institutions requires knowledge of data management competencies, data management workflows, incentives for FAIR in practice, access to infrastructure, guidelines, information about the value of data, and information on stakeholder involvement in the development of FAIR, and not least, how the various initiatives connect with and to issues of security and sensitive data.

The chairpersons of the working groups have internally cooperated and communicated on the focus areas to identify where one area overlaps with another and have looked at interdisciplinary opportunities. Internal and external communication is increasingly important to ensure that knowledge and recommendations about the development of the FAIR principles are available to universities in Denmark.

This annual report contains sections from each working group as well as some concluding comments. The second mandate period extends until the end of 2025, and therefore, some focus areas will be carried over to the 2025 annual report.

¹ Remit for the FAIR Reference group 2023-24: DOI [10.5281/zenodo.10653489](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10653489). (Extended until ultimo 2025)

² Report for the National Strategy for Data Management based on the FAIR Principals (2022) DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7575580](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7575580). (In danish)

3. Communication and knowledge exchange on data management and FAIR

Internal and external communication

Goal 0.1. Communication support to be established across the 6 working groups, where members of the working groups can find information about, for example:

- Policies
- Strategies
- Tools
- Q&A Manuals
- International references
- Litterature
- Courses related to FAIR and Data Management

Reporting: Communication channels have been established for the working groups on Microsoft Teams, where members can find information about the above, as well as store agendas, minutes, and other materials, and communicate internally easily, and without disruption.

Goal 0.2: An open and public channel will be established for publication of relevant materials from the working groups and the FAIR Reference group.

Reporting: A channel has been established on Zenodo for the FAIR strategy, [mandate period 2023-2025](#). The chairpersons of the working groups have internal collaboration and communication about the focus areas to explore interdisciplinary opportunities.

4. Working group A – Policies, tools, and research support for FAIR data management

Working Group A addresses the FAIR Reference group's focus areas 1, 2, and 3.

Focus area 1

How do different disciplines implement the FAIR principles in research practices? For example, in their specific workflows, tools, etc., possibly drawing inspiration from/in collaboration with international research environments.

Goal(s):

Examples of subject-specific workflows and tools from selected disciplines across various academic fields.

Reporting:

Working group A has prepared a report³ where we provide examples from different specific disciplines on their current implementation of FAIR practices.

The examples are from,

- a. University of Copenhagen, Dept. Nutrition, Exercise and Sports, Section for Nutrition.
- b. Aarhus University, Dept. Agroecology
- c. DTU Biosustain

The questions answered in the section are,

1. How do the policies affect the daily work with data management and data sharing?
2. How do we in practice collaborate?
3. Which tools are available?

Recommendation(s):

The working group has made a list of challenges and recommendations.

- **Challenge:** Some research groups have challenges in gaining access to research support for FAIRification, which enables their research data and research infrastructure to be FAIR-by-Design, i.e. projects are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable from the start.
Recommendation: The universities and DeIC should evaluate the research support (which to some extent is provided by the universities' IT departments and the research libraries), as it does not seem to have the necessary skills and sufficient scope to provide the research support that is demanded.

- **Challenge:** It is difficult for research support units to attract competent IT and data management expertise (data stewards), partly because the job profile is rarely at a sufficient level of competence, and partly because the job market and salary situation make it difficult.

³ Appendix - Working Group A – Policies, tools, and research support for FAIR data management. Report 2023-2024

Recommendation: As advanced research support requires high-level competences, consideration should be given to offering the most advanced research support nationally, with the aim of the best possible coordination and achieving a critical mass of competence.

Recommendation: The universities should reassess how research support is organised, financed and offered (locally and nationally).

- **Challenge:** Some research groups have challenges in handling, analysing and integrating large and complex amounts of data; this applies locally, nationally and internationally.
- **Recommendation:** Universities should support the establishment of discipline-specific data science labs and centres. These must be able to support the local research IT infrastructure, stimulate collaborative work, and ensure effective data integration between data science labs in Denmark. This will also enable the discipline-specific environments to collaborate with international data science labs and EU frameworks (e.g. [INSPIRE](#)), and it will make the research groups attractive partners in research projects.
- **Challenge:** The need for research IT support and infrastructure development is comprehensive, but there can be uncertainty about where competencies and responsibilities should be placed – nationally at DeiC, at the university, at the faculty, the institute, the research group, the individual researcher. Likewise, how research IT and administrative IT support and infrastructure can play together and support each other.

Recommendation: A mapping of the cons and pros of different solutions should be conducted based on an analysis of how different universities have worked with these issues.

Appendices:

- Appendix - Working Group A – Policies, tools, and research support for FAIR data management. Report 2023-2024

Focus area 2

What policies and motivating/supportive measures exist to support access to and reuse of research data, including the use of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for digital research objects (data, software, instruments, publications, etc.)?

Goal(s):

To collect examples of motivating and supporting efforts to access and reuse research data, at universities and selected research institutions.

Reporting:

The working group has collected and summarised data management policies and examples of supporting measures from the eight Danish universities, GEUS, The National Archives, and The Royal Danish Library. Examples of faculty level information has been collected from Aarhus University and University of Copenhagen.

All universities have a policy or rules for handling research data, and most of them relate to the Danish Code of Conduct for Research Integrity from 2014 and the FAIR principles from 2016. Some universities and research institutions are currently revising their data management policies. The Danish Code of Conduct for Research Integrity is undergoing a revision and is expected to be published in a new version in 2025.

Whom do the policies apply to?

In general, the policies apply to employees, visiting staff and others involved in research activities. Most universities specifically mention students, but at AAU, AU and DTU students are only included when they carry out research or contribute to research under the auspices of the universities. Including students in the data management policies can present some challenges, as students belong to a different legal framework than researchers. This raises questions such as: What are the requirements for data storage and deletion of data? Should students be considered in data processing agreements?

Openness of data

Researchers are encouraged to make their data openly available according to the FAIR principles, i.e. as open as possible, as closed as necessary. There is a distinction between primary data and data underlying publications. Primary data may contain personal or confidential information or form the basis of further publications and therefore not suitable to be open, whereas data supporting research findings may be necessary for replication and validation of the findings. The right to share data depends on the ownership to the data, which may be shared between several parties. At AU, primary data owned by the university can only be shared with third parties following a written agreement with the head of department. DTU and UCPH recommend that rights to data and terms and conditions for reuse are determined at the beginning or planning of a project. At AAU, researchers are warned against transferring rights to data if this prevents the researchers from using the data for later research.

Use of persistent identifiers

Incorporating persistent identifiers into data management strategies is vital for enhancing accessibility, discoverability, and usability of research outputs. By ensuring that datasets are uniquely identified and easily retrievable over time, researchers can contribute more effectively to the academic community while promoting best practices in data sharing and citation.

Persistent identifiers are only mentioned specifically in a few data management policies (RUC and DTU), but they are part of the services offered by many repositories. At AAU DOIs are offered for datasets published solely in the university's research portal. In the forthcoming DeIC Dataverse, it will be possible to issue DOIs to datasets published in the repository.

Support

All universities offer support for data management, either as a centralised service or as a faculty-level service. Often, more parties are involved in the support, e.g. IT, legal, research support, the library. Information and help is also available on the universities' websites, in one case in the form of a support ticket system.

Recommendation(s):

New infrastructure for publishing and storing data is on the way in the form of DeIC Storage, DeIC Sensitive Storage, and DeIC Dataverse. The working group recommends accelerating the adoption of these services and assessing the impact they may have on researchers' data sharing practices. **It is recommended** that national infrastructure (e.g. DeIC Storage, DeIC Sensitive Storage, and DeIC Dataverse) be firmly anchored in international cooperation as to the specific infrastructure implementation and operations.

It is recommended that the universities explicitly formulate and adopt local data management and PID policies, relating to use of national and international infrastructure.

Challenge: It is a challenge to establish the needed governance for the trusted data repositories.

Recommendation: Danish Universities agree on a governance structure supported by the needed expertise and a network of staff anchored across the Universities and in cooperation with DeIC.

Appendices:

- Appendix - Working Group A – Policies, tools, and research support for FAIR data management. Report 2023-2024

Focus area 3

Describe best practices for data governance and policies/guidelines for overseeing overall data responsibility, even after researchers have left the institution and/or project funding has ceased.

Goal(s):

Identification of best practices for data governance and policies to manage the overall responsibility for data.

Reporting:

As evidenced from the descriptions in the report, best practices can be different, depending on the research area, data type, and legal constraints, among others. One of the more general points for developing a best practice is to have a clear data management plan that includes the vision for making data FAIR and if possible, also openly shared over time.

Recommendation(s):

Challenge: It is a challenge that data sometimes are lost, and the understanding and proper use of data depends on individuals.

Recommendations: Support the data science labs (DSL) and centres in developing IT ecosystems that at the local level can make data, tools and services FAIR. The DSLs and centres should also stimulate the FAIRification of the research process itself.

Challenge: More data stewards are now being employed at the research institutions. Their role is also to take care of data governance, support the effective data life cycle adoption and secure data in the long term. Often one or a few people support an institute.

Recommendations: The universities should support the education and employment of more data stewards, and the establishment of a university network of data stewards to exchange experiences and ideas about relevant support and infrastructures.

Appendices:

- Appendix - Working Group A – Policies, tools, and research support for FAIR data management. Report 2023-2024

5. Working group B – Establishing FAIR infrastructure and long term preservation

Working Group B addresses the FAIR Reference group's focus areas 4, 5 and 6.

Focus area 4

What infrastructure is available for the long-term preservation (10+ years) of research data of any kind at the national level, and how is coherence and collaboration ensured between research institutions, DeiC, and the National Archives regarding long-term preservation?

Goal(s):

There were two goals for this focus area in 2024:

1. To survey which Danish infrastructures offer long-term preservation of research data. Initially, research data repositories were surveyed, but subsequently, the connection to storage infrastructures will also be included. These two types of infrastructure, run by research institutions or DeiC, will be examined to determine whether they offer long-term preservation. Long-term preservation in this context means a guarantee that data remains accessible for research over a long period of time
2. To examine to what extent the danish universities needs' for long-term preservation are met by DeiC's strategy for long-term preservation.

Reporting:

Reporting on the two goals for the focus area:

1. None of the repositories surveyed offer actual long-term preservation, understood as bit preservation and/or logical preservation, with the exception of the National Archives (Rigsarkivet). Some repositories explicitly mention a specific period for which data is guaranteed to be stored (e.g., 10 years), but most either have no specific goals or do not have publicly available information on this. Eight repositories without this information were contacted, and six responded. None of the known repositories demonstrate the same level of long-term preservation as the National Archives, which is likely due to this type of service requiring specialised technology and expertise.
2. DeiC has not yet finalised and published its long-term preservation strategy, therefore reporting on this goal will be possible at a later date.

Recommendation(s):

Not all data can or should be preserved indefinitely. There must be a realistic balance between the value of the data and the costs associated with long-term preservation—a key focus of Working Group F. Therefore, the following is recommended for this focus area:

1. Distinguish between three time horizons for data preservation:
 - A. Short-term: Data to be preserved for up to 10 years
 - B. Medium-term: Data typically preserved for 10-30 years to benefit active research
 - C. Long-term: Data to be preserved indefinitely for posterity
2. Define criteria (e.g., reproducibility and resources connected to reproducibility, and the research data value – cost and research value,) to determine the appropriate preservation horizon (short,

medium, or long-term) for each dataset. In this context, reference is also made to Working Group F – Datas Valuation.

3. For medium-term preservation, identify and/or establish infrastructure capable of handling long-term preservation of this data type. Logical preservation (e.g., format monitoring and migration) will likely be less critical, with a greater emphasis on bit-level preservation of the original formats. Working group B considers this timeframe most relevant for its future work.
4. Long-term preservation for posterity, focusing on logical preservation, should primarily be handled by the National Archives (Rigsarkivet), as this task requires specialised knowledge and infrastructure.
 - a. Focus on developing technical solutions that enables researchers to easily submit and potentially transfer data to the National Archives for long-term preservation. The reasoning being that highly specialised expertise is required for logical long term preservation, making it unsuitable for individual research institutions or DeiC. Integration of DeiC's storage and repository infrastructures with the National Archives would potentially increase the number of submissions and subsequent data transfers, but this requires collaborative development of user-friendly solutions among research institutions, DeiC, and the National Archives to avoid creating an unreasonably large workload. This type of integration with the National Archives' submission function should be developed across all relevant infrastructures for optimal ease of use for researchers submitting this type of data.

Appendices:

- Appendix - Working Group B - Danish data repositories and long-term preservation 2024⁴

Focus area 5:

How can services for data management planning continue to be developed nationally and internationally, and how can data management plans be made machine-readable, and be used in connection with the submission of research data to the National Archives?

Data Management Plans (DMPs) have the potential to improve several aspects of research, including:

- **Data quality assurance:** By establishing clear protocols for data collection, storage, and handling, a DMP ensures that data is accurate, complete, and reliable. This is crucial for high-quality research results
- **Increased Reproducibility:** A DMP promotes transparency in the research process by documenting all methods and data handling practices, making it easier for other researchers to reproduce the results
- **Data Security:** A DMP helps ensure that data requiring protection—including data subject to GDPR, intellectual property rights, dual-use categories, or sensitive business data—is handled correctly
- **Resource Management and Allocation:** A DMP assists researchers in efficiently selecting and coordinating the resources and infrastructure used to create and process data

⁴ List of repositories with Danish co-ownership or participation. This list excludes repositories receiving data from Danish researchers but lacking Danish organisations in their governance.

- Self-Determination and Digital Sovereignty: A DMP can empower researchers to better control their own data and enhance the digital sovereignty of institutions
- Compliance with Regulations and Standards: A DMP helps ensure compliance with relevant laws, standards, etc. For example, notification and delivery to the National Archives
- Data Discovery and Reuse: By implementing standards for data archiving and metadata, the potential for other researchers to discover and reuse data is increased. This can lead to new collaborations and enhance the impact of research

The assesment of this working group is that many DMPs are primarily created because they are required for project applications, and therefore their current value is limited.

Goal(s):

A DMP should provide value to the researcher and be an integral part of project management, for example, as an active/living document where the DMP forms part of the overall project documentation, alongside laboratory data and results. To ensure long-term access and stability in working methods, it is necessary to use open-source programs from the university sector. This eliminates the risk of vendor lock-in during competitive tendering and ensures that the tools remain available and maintained.

Reporting:

Many researchers encounter a DMP as a fixed template or form to be filled out, which can limit the flexibility and relevance of the DMP in relation to the researcher's specific needs and research projects. Based on a questionnaire survey, the group will illuminate the current use of DMPs among Danish researchers. The group has compiled a list of software systems for working with DMPs and will, in further work, analyse these systems in terms of functionality, prevalence, use, and potential for automation.

Recommendation(s):

For several years, various stakeholders have required the creation of a DMP in connection with research projects. It is important to gather experiences from these requirements to assess the relationship between the value achieved and the workload imposed on researchers by the DMP process. The aim is to identify best practices that can be used and supported by research infrastructures to ensure that DMPs become an efficient and value-creating tool in research.

Appendices:

- Appendix - Working Group B – Overview of data management plan tools 2024

Focus area 6

Elaborate on how research institutions work with security infrastructure (Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting Infrastructure, AAAI) specifically and especially for sensitive data, with the aim of also making these FAIR.

AAAI stands for 'Authentication, Authorisation, and Accounting Infrastructure,' a term used within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). It serves as an umbrella term encompassing all aspects of identity management, login processes, and resource organisation, and usage accounting for the administration of digital resources. Other commonly used terms for this area include:

- Trust and Identity (T&I)
- Identity and Access Management (IAM)
- Digital Asset Management (DAM)

WAYF (Where Are You From) is Denmark's identity federation for research and education. WAYF acts as a central infrastructure linking identity providers with service providers in the research and education sectors. WAYF allows users to log into external services using their existing institutional login credentials.

Service providers and data owners face increasing demands to demonstrate that their infrastructures and data are not misused by sanctioned entities or malicious actors. This necessitates enhanced identity verification within the federation, a requirement that will impact Danish universities in their role as identity providers within the WAYF federation within the next 1-3 years.

Goal(s):

The goal is to ensure that researchers at Danish research institutions and private research companies have access to research data and resources, while adhering to stringent security and data protection standards, via a reliable and secure identity infrastructure. This will allow for meeting both data owners' security requirements and researchers' need for access to essential resources within a secure framework.

Reporting:

The Danish national identity federation (WAYF) is a recognised member of the global research and education identity federation (eduGAIN) and a respected identity broker for Danish identity providers, including universities and their service providers. WAYF also acts as a broker for NemID, providing Danish universities with easy and free access to MitID.

Recommendation(s):

The group has postponed a deeper analysis of research institutions' use of identity and security infrastructure until 2025. This decision is based on the fact that nearly all standard-setting stakeholders are planning to release updated versions of requirements and standards in 2025 in response to a changing threat landscape. This will allow the group to consider these updated requirements and standards in its analysis.

It is however, already clear that identity verification requirements will become stricter. Denmark is well-prepared to meet these requirements through the government's implementation of MitID.

DeiC has the opportunity, through dialogue with the Danish universities, to find the best way to prepare the Danish identity federation to meet these increased demands. This should focus on leveraging MitID to enhance identity verification within the WAYF federation and ensure that the universities' affiliation with identities is reported in accordance with the eduGAIN federation's standards.

Appendices:

No appendices.

6. Working group C – Financial plan for FAIR data

Working Group C addresses the FAIR Reference group's focus areas 7, 8 and 9.

Focus area 7

EU programs (e.g., Horizon Europe) require grant recipients to develop data management plans in connection with grant applications. To what extent can national research funding organizations benefit from following this practice?

Goal(s):

To map best practices for data management plans across various research disciplines, and to chart the types and levels of expenditure on data management in specific projects. Concurrently, the group will examine current practices regarding requirements for Data Management Plans (DMPs) among Danish funding bodies and Horizon Europe, and, in the longer term, assess the potential for standardising requirements and procedures across Danish funding bodies with respect to DMPs.

Reporting:

Data Management Plans: Recommendations, templates, and examples exist

Several general recommendations exist for researchers⁵ when creating a data management plan. A DMP-template, created by recognised organisations such as Science Europe or Horizon Europe, can be used to structure the plan so that all FAIR data management aspects are covered. Templates for data management plans can be found at dmp.deic.dk, among other places. Examples of data management plans from completed research projects are also available on this site.

Procedures regarding requirements for FAIR and Data Management Plans at Danish public research foundations

The three major Danish public research funding bodies— The Danish National Research Foundation (GF), Independent Research Fund Denmark (DFF), and Innovation Fund Denmark (IFD) have a homogenous approach to FAIR, in that they do not explicitly require participating parties (public or private, including international entities) to adhere to the FAIR principles for project-generated data. Furthermore, there is no knowledge of other publicly funded bodies or government programs (including EUDP, GUDP, and MUDP⁶) that mandate or recommend adherence to the FAIR principles. However, GF, DFF, and IFD do recommend adherence to the FAIR principles, though they do not track compliance.

These public funding bodies do therefore not actively ensure compliance with the FAIR principles. Compliance may occur if a participating party's own organisation mandates it, such as if a participating university ensures adherence to the FAIR principles.

Regarding Data Management Plans (DMPs), the situation is similar, with one exception: IFD requires DMPs for projects within the Grand Solutions program and the four green missions. These two programs comprise

⁵ DMPOnline, On data management planning. <https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/help>

⁶ EUDP: The Energy Technology Development and Demonstration Programme, GUDP: Grønt Udviklings- og Demonstrationsprogram, MUDP: Miljøteknisk Udviklings- og Demonstrationsprogram

approximately 50% of IFD's budget and are the only IFD programs deemed relevant by the fund for DMP creation. IFD mandates DMP creation in connection with the signing of a contract for a given project. Applicants are therefore informed of this requirement at the application stage, if they receive funding, but it is not part of the application itself nor its evaluation, including the extent, nature, and quality of the planned data management work. IFD supports DMP creation by referring to commonly used templates from DeiC and the EU. DMPs are generally considered a deliverable within a project (potentially updated iteratively) and are included in IFD's project follow-up model.

In summary, as of autumn 2024, adherence to the FAIR principles and creation of DMPs largely depends on the participating parties themselves, regardless of the public funding source. However, the largest funds recommend, and one fund mandates, the creation of DMPs.

Procedures regarding data management plan requirements in private Danish foundations:

Without conducting a systematic survey, the working group's preliminary findings and discussions suggest that private Danish foundations largely do not explicitly require the submission of DMPs with applications and funding approvals. However, some foundations, such as the Novo Nordisk Foundation, have programs where plans for data and code sharing are explicitly mentioned as evaluation criteria for applications. However, there are often no specific requirements for submitting a formal data management plan.

Reccomendation(s):

Based on this status, the working group recommends:

- That the working group surveys the rules and principles at universities regarding following up on DMPs and FAIR practices.
- Examining the secondary effects of requiring DMPs from researchers and foundations. This includes analysing the risk of increased costs and secondary effects for all parties, if the party making the requirement (a foundation) does not specify the requirements more precisely
- Examining the advantages and disadvantages of requiring DMPs at different stages of the project process.

Appendices:

No appendices.

Focus area 8

Can the research data that is the basis for published research results, be required to be made available according to FAIR principles after the project's completion, at a minimum with metadata and a Persistent Identifier (PID), even when the data is not openly accessible?

Goal(s):

To explore current and future possibilities for registering (assigning PIDs) and sharing metadata for sensitive data sets, as well as any associated challenges and barriers.

Reporting:

With the introduction of DeiC Dataverse and DeiC Storage, researchers and students at Danish universities have two new tools to help make research data FAIR. Dataverse is a catalogue of metadata associated with research data. The DeiC Storage system provides everyone with a minimum amount of storage space for electronic objects—data, algorithms, programs, etc.—that are minimally required to reproduce a published research result. The intention is to allow storage space to be expanded upon application to DeiC's ressource

committee, or, for very large needs, by purchasing additional storage space through DeiC. Digital objects can be assigned a PID, and locked to prevent future changes to their content. It is expected that the DeiC data repository will be further expanded at the beginning of 2025 with DeiC Sensitive Storage, which will also be able to handle sensitive data.

Once objects are stored in the DeiC data repository, the user can choose to make the data accessible to others, either publicly or with restricted access. Sensitive data will always be either inaccessible to others or have restricted access. The level of openness will be described in the metadata (e.g., in DeiC Dataverse) associated with a set of digital objects.

Eventually, the plan is to make the system a national Danish EOSC-node. This will allow Danish research data to be presented to and accessed by other researchers in a controlled manner. Rules and protocols for access are currently under development. A prototype EOSC-node is under development, and DeiC is awaiting the test results before making a final decision on whether to build a Danish EOSC-node.

Regarding archiving of electronic objects (i.e., storage beyond 10 years), DeiC's board has decided to ask the FAIR Reference group to propose a Danish plan for long-term preservation of electronic objects.

In addition to the possibilities of DeiC Dataverse and DeiC Storage, there are numerous national and international possibilities for registering, storing, and sharing research data using persistent identifiers and metadata, with some supporting the handling of sensitive data⁷. For example, in the PURE research information system, used by several Danish universities, it is possible to register metadata for datasets, upload datasets up to 5 GB, obtain persistent identifiers, and control access.

Reccomendation(s):

Given the establishment of a national repository for research data with corresponding metadata descriptions in a trusted repository (DeiC Dataverse), the focus area could be rephrased as follows:

How can we ensure that research data and other electronic objects underlying published research results are stored in accordance with FAIR principles after the project ends, including at minimum a Persistent Identifier (PID) and publicly available metadata, even if the data is not openly accessible?

Appendices:

No appendices.

Focus area 9

What costs related to data management can be included in budgets?

Goal(s):

To clarify when and how costs for data management are considered covered by general categories, such as overhead or indirect project supplements, and when they can be included as itemised expenses in a grant application budget. The aim is to achieve maximum consistency across funding bodies, while acknowledging that current practices vary between them (e.g., overhead costs at the Danish National Research Foundation versus a new indirect project supplement at the five private foundations).

⁷ See for instance. https://gatesopenresearch.org/for-authors/data-guidelines?utm_source=Gatesblog&utm_medium=cms&utm_campaign=JRJ32360#hosting

Reporting:

Across funding bodies and universities, the general trend is that data management costs are included—and accepted—in research project budgets. None of the group's participants, nor the stakeholders they have interacted with, have experienced grant applications being rejected due to data management related expenses. However, budget categories and data management practices vary across research fields, universities, funding bodies, and sometimes even between programs within the same funding body. Funding bodies could therefore benefit from greater transparency regarding their principles for covering data management related expenses and the possibility of including such expenses in grant applications.

In most projects, the largest data management related expenses are salaries for personnel performing tasks such as annotating, formatting, FAIRifying, and sharing data. In many projects, these expenses are not explicitly itemised in budgets as "data management expenses" but instead appear as salaries for PhD students, post-docs, etc. In addition, there are costs associated with storing and sharing data after project completion (or upon publication). With the launch of services like DeIC storage and DeIC Dataverse, these costs are expected to become more visible in budgets in the future, as sharing and depositing large datasets may incur fees payable by the project, in accordance with the data management strategy's categories (1, 2A, 2B, and 3)⁸

Working Group C has examined the allocation of the indirect supplemental funding recently agreed upon between universities and many of the larger Danish research foundations⁹. The philosophy behind this supplemental funding is that for selected areas of expenses (for instance IT expenses) the parties involved operate with an agreed contribution, to cover the expenses in an ordinary, typical project (referred to as 'basis' or 'standard' in the agreement). Projects where expenses significantly exceed this average level must seek coverage for these additional expenses directly through their grant application (referred to in the agreement as 'extraordinary' or 'special').

The calculation and agreement basis for the indirect supplemental funding shows that it is intended to finance a "standard package" of IT expenses, including certain data management related expenses. However, these amounts are small and likely insufficient to cover actual data management costs in disciplines working with large datasets. The relatively low estimates are likely due to the fact that the data used for the calculations come from budgets of previous (historical) projects where data management expenses, as noted above, are often not explicitly itemised but rather appear as salary expenses. Furthermore, costs associated with data sharing and storage (e.g., disk space) were probably not included in the data used for projects conducted before the EU Open Data Directive (2019) and the Danish Data Management Strategy (2021).

Therefore, the calculation basis for the indirect supplemental funding does not significantly include data management costs, meaning that, in dataintensive projects, direct coverage of such costs must be sought. The agreement, however, stipulates that the supplement and the agreement itself will be revisited by the parties involved for renegotiation and adjustment.

Overhead at public research foundations

To support the implementation of the FAIR principles in research projects, current practices were examined regarding which types of data management expenses are considered covered by overhead contributions from public research funds, including the Independent Research Fund Denmark and The Innovation Fund

⁸ de Lichtenberg, N. U., Hansen, R. J., Lindberg, B., Arleth, L., Christensen-Dalsgaard, B., Andreasen, M., Drongstrup, D., & Larsen, B. (2022). Arbejdsgruppe C - Tabel over udgifter. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7413725>

⁹ Danske Universiteter. Aftale mellem universiteter og fonde om finansiering af forskningsprojekter. <https://dkuni.dk/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/aftaletekst-endelig-version.pdf>

Denmark. The study was based on previously developed categorisations of FAIR-related expenses, such as salaries for data managers, data storage costs, data cleaning, and software.

The findings indicate that expenses directly supporting FAIR principles rarely receive separate funding from these funds, as they are most often covered by the overhead allocation. Overhead is intended to cover basic operations and essential facilities, meaning that expenses for specialised data management tasks—such as long-term data storage, use of advanced software, and secure data management—are often not specifically addressed. However, the full-funding principle ensures that projects are seldom reduced in scope, allowing projects to allocate funds flexibly to FAIR-related needs within their overall budget.

Internal management of indirect supplemental funding and overhead at Danish universities:

Currently, indirect supplemental funding and overhead funds are received by universities as a single lump sum for covering indirect costs. There are no stipulations regarding the specific allocation of these funds across cost categories. Therefore, specific cost drivers do not have a claim to a portion of the project supplement or overhead. Within the framework set by the funding body, the allocation of project supplements and overhead is entirely at the discretion of the university itself.

Long-Term Preservation:

A particular challenge relates to the long-term preservation of data in repositories such as DeIC storage and DeIC Dataverse. The current model involves a fee for sharing datasets exceeding a certain size over a defined period (e.g., 5-10 years). However, the group anticipates a significant challenge after this period in determining the value of continued data storage (this will be addressed by the working group, along with a discussion of how long-term preservation should be financed).

Reccomendation(s):

The working group recommends continued dialogue between universities and funding bodies to address the lack of visibility of data management expenses in budgets and financial reports. In the next period, the working group will investigate the best way to communicate its conclusions to the relevant stakeholders.

Appendices:

No appendices

7. Working group D- Plan for structuring and developing FAIR competencies and knowledge

Working Group D addresses the FAIR Reference group's focus areas 10, 11, 12, and 13. The group has categorised the focus areas and related actions into three topics: (1) Data Stewardship, (2) National Competence Center, and (3) Recognition and Rewarding regarding FAIR Data Management

(D1) Data Stewardship

Focus area 10

(D1) What competence profiles have research institutions established for the Data Stewardship research support function for researchers? How have research institutions built the Data Stewardship research support function for researchers?

Goal(s):

- Mapping of the organisational data management landscape in Denmark
- Mapping of the competency landscape of data management in Denmark

Reporting:

Currently, there is a quite fragmented landscape of data stewardship support functions at the Danish universities. Only Aalborg University has invested in creating a central [data stewardship support function](#) at [CLAAUDIA](#), where four data stewards were hired in early 2023. The other universities do not offer centralised data stewardship support functions. Instead, data stewards work at the faculty level, e.g. in the [Social Sciences Data Lab](#) of the University of Copenhagen, or in research centres or projects, e.g. at the [Novo Nordisk Foundation Center for Biosustainability](#) at the Technical University of Denmark or at the [Novo Nordisk Foundation Center for Stem Cell Medicine](#) at the University of Copenhagen.

We see a similar situation regarding formal data stewardship education. There have been initiatives at several universities, but so far only the University of Southern Denmark offers a [Master's degree programme in data stewardship](#) (from September 2025).

Given these diverse approaches to organising institutional data stewardship support and offering competence development, working group D.1 decided to collect more data on how data stewards work and what services they offer at Danish research institutions. Data will be collected with a survey and, in a second step, complemented with semi-structured interviews. We expect that the data will allow us to draw a more complete picture of the Danish data stewardship landscape in 2025, and that we will be able to provide concrete recommendations on how to consolidate and further mature data stewardship initiatives in Denmark.

The survey was designed on the backdrop of the goals and actions described in the action plan for working group D and also relates to the "minimum viable skill set (MVS)" for data stewards that has been created in the Skills4EOSC project (Whyte, A. et al. (2023). D2.1 Catalogue of Open Science Career Profiles - Minimum Viable Skillsets (v1.2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8101903> & White, A., & Green, D. (2024). Data Steward: Minimum Viable Skills Profile. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14006764>). It is aimed at technical and administrative staff as well as researchers working with data stewardship tasks in a broader sense, regardless of job titles. Relevant job titles include data steward, data librarian, data manager, research

data specialist, research data manager, research data coordinator, data scientist, or data curator. The survey also targets researchers that perform peer-to-peer support, e.g. in a data lab, or researchers that have taken on the role of a data steward in their research group.

The survey contains 14 questions and is divided into three sections: (1) The organisation of the local data stewardship support function, (2) Professional development opportunities for data stewards, and (3) Professional background and job title.

Currently, the survey is piloted with relevant stakeholders. After the piloting phase, it will be broadly distributed at the research institutions, among others through the universities' Front Offices.

Reccomendation(s):

Working group D.1 cannot give any recommendations at this point. We expect to give recommendations regarding national initiatives for data stewardship competency development on:

- Whether there is a need to invest more resources and hire more data stewards,
- Whether there is a need for more learning opportunities within parts of the data lifecycle,
- Whether these learning opportunities should be nationally coordinated (for example in the form of a national competence center).

Appendices:

No appendices.

(D2) National Competence center

Focus area 11

To what extent is there interest in developing and offering the research support function collectively at the national level? For example, under a central or decentralized national competence center.

Focus area 12

Is there interest among research institutions in national coordination of educational offerings (not research support) within FAIR research data management? Can a potential national collaboration aim at division of labor, specialisation, and joint national offerings of educational programs, such as through a competence center under the auspices of DeIC? This includes education at all levels, from bachelor to further education of scientific staff.

Goal(s):

- Presentation of international case studies of how national competence centers for FAIR data management are organised and what services they offer
- Presentation of an organisational model and potential services of a Danish national competence center
- Overview of institutional needs and interests regarding national coordination of FAIR data management education and training in Denmark

Reporting:

Working group D.2 investigates the need for national coordination of FAIR data stewardship training and education in Denmark. National coordination could for instance be organised in a **national competence center (NCC) for data stewardship, as outlined by the [Skills4EOSC project](#)**:

“In the Skills4EOSC’s vision, Competence Centres (S4E CCs) are dedicated to knowledge organization and transfer in the Open Science, FAIR research output management and EOSC context, in their countries, region or thematic domain. They address the skills shortage by offering to training, including workforce upskilling and reskilling on Open Science. They connect stakeholders to national and international programs linked to OS and EOSC and act as an access point to network on OS and FAIR research. They are usually associated with excellence, training and knowledge transfer, interdisciplinarity, standardization, and a collaborative approach of different institutions or departments. The structure, operational mode and organization of Competence Centres may vary very widely” ([Skills4EOSC Competence Centre Charter](#)).

As a first step, NCC case studies have been gathered from four northern European countries with whom Denmark actively collaborates via Knowledge Exchange: Finland, UK, the Netherlands, and Germany. The case studies were chosen, because these NCCs can provide insight into possible configurations of constituting factors like funding, government relations, university sector representation etc. The purpose of the case studies is to gather different NCC-models, to describe and compare their defining traits, and on this basis to approximate a relevant model for Denmark.

The analysis of the four northern European case studies shows that NCCs can be organised in different ways. IT Center for Science (CSC) in Finland, for instance, is a non-profit organisation partially owned by the Finnish state, Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS) in Holland, as well as UK Data Service (UK) are funded by national research councils, while National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) is a large, federated initiative financed by the German state. Others again like SURF (NL) and Joint Information Systems Committee (JISC) in the UK are non-profit organisations financed through a mix of member contributions, service fees, and government grants. There are also differences in terms of services, with some NCCs focusing more on delivering state-of-the-art research infrastructures (SURF, JISC), while others offer a mix of access to research infrastructures and competence development (CSC, DANS, UK Data Service, NFDI).

Furthermore, we have included some questions in the survey of group D.1 to get an idea of data stewards’ needs for professional development coordination in Denmark. We expect the survey to shed light on whether there is an actual need that could justify establishing a NCC in Denmark.

The next step is to expand the scope of the case studies to include case studies from relevant southern European countries, namely France (also a member of Knowledge Exchange), Italy, and Austria, all of which are viewed as successful examples of NCCs. We will then draft the outlines of a potential Danish NCC for data stewardship and discuss this proposal with different stakeholders like individual data stewards (“bottom-up”) and decision-makers (“top-down”).

Reccomendation(s):

We recommend that the FAIR Reference group supports the organisation of a workshop with high-level decision makers within Danish academia where the organisation and funding of a potential Danish NCC would be discussed.

Appendices:

No appendices.

(D3) Recognition and Rewarding regarding FAIR Data Management

Focus area 13

How are incentive structures or merit systems currently used nationally or internationally for FAIR data management practices at research institutions?

Goal(s):

- Overview of national or international recommendations for how to reward FAIR data management practices
- Mapping of current incentive structures for FAIR data management practices at Danish universities
- Mapping of current incentive structures for FAIR data management internationally

Reporting:

During the past 15 years an increasing number of international initiatives have formulated recommendations to reward open science and FAIR data management practices. It seems that the research community only recently started to emphasise the importance of rewarding open science and FAIR data management practices, but this is a process slowly building up momentum.

The [San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment \(DORA\)](#) from 2012 advocates for recognising researchers who share data openly and promote transparency. The [European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\) Declaration \(2017\)](#) encourages rewarding researchers who share open and FAIR data in career assessments and project evaluations. In 2022, the Council of the European Union published their [Conclusions on Research assessment and implementation of Open Science](#) toward promoting and rewarding Open Science, considering this a mechanism for reinforcing research integrity and a driver of the quality and impact of science to the benefit of society. Similarly, the [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment \(CoARA\)](#) calls institutions in their [Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment \(2022\)](#) to develop and evaluate new assessment criteria and tools that will raise awareness, reward researchers, and inform policies on research outputs associated with openness. The 2023 [ALLEA European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) highlights good research practices, including the management, protection, and transparency of data and research materials, ensuring reproducibility, traceability, and accountability. The 2024 [Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information](#) promotes collective action to accelerate the transition to openness in research information, ensuring transparency and accountability in research assessments.

National initiatives and institutional awards also play a significant role in promoting open science. In France, for example, the [Open Science Research Data and Open Science Free Software Awards](#) recognises efforts in structuring, describing, interoperating, and enhancing the visibility of research data for both researchers and research projects. The [Berlin Institute of Health](#) offers various monetary Open Science Awards to encourage projects that promote open science in categories such as open access, open data, transparency, and societal impact. The [University of Groningen's Open Research Award](#) celebrates openness in research and teaching, inviting case studies via nominations that explore the benefits and challenges of open practices. The [Leo Waaijers Award](#) in the Netherlands recognises bold, innovative, and impactful initiatives in open science for individual researchers or groups. [Aalto University](#) in Finland celebrates community members who promote open science in research or teaching through its Open Science Award, with nominations highlighting activities related to data, publications, software, and methods. [Lübeck University](#) (Germany) aims to raise awareness and promote open science within the university through its Open Science Award, recognising projects that excel in transparency, reproducibility, and open communication. The [UCL Open Science & Scholarship Award](#) (UK) highlights exceptional practices and support for open science across the university, with categories for students, non-academic staff, open publishing, and more.

In Denmark, new perspectives on research assessment and open science are discussed at many institutions, but we are looking at a fragmented landscape. Aalborg University emphasises with the [AAU Research](#)

[Indicator](#) a shift towards a broader perspective in research evaluation, incorporating both quantitative and qualitative metrics to better reflect the diversity of research impact. [UCViden](#), the university colleges' research portal, introduces a new practice dissemination indicator to document the societal contribution of university of applied sciences research, including non-traditional outputs like reports and podcasts. The [DTU Research Analytics Platform \(DTU RAP\)](#) features collaboration and bibliometric indicators for research evaluation, focusing on internal and external collaborations and publication metrics. SDU Library proposes a new person-centered indicator, [OADO](#), for assessing openness in research and communication activities, combining factors of open access, open data, and open outreach. Danish Universities (DKUNI), finally, created a [framework for advancing competencies and experiences within impact](#), providing a tool for assessing research activities and emphasising the importance of open science, impact, and collaboration in academic evaluations. Lastly, we expect the results from the [Data Stewardship Questionnaire](#) (sub-group D.1) to shed more light on existing practices in Denmark.

Overall, there is an evolving landscape of research assessment and reward initiatives, both for individual researchers and teams/projects, emphasising the importance of open science and data management best practices at both international and national levels. It showcases various initiatives and awards that recognise and promote transparency, data sharing, and collaboration in research, aiming to foster a more open and inclusive scientific community.

Reccomendation(s):

Working group D.3 cannot give any recommendations at this point. We expect to be able to give specific recommendations regarding FAIR DM rewards/awards at the Danish research institutions in the next annual report.

Appendices:

No appendices.

8. Working group E – Security aspects of FAIR data collaboration

Working Group E addresses the FAIR Reference group's focus areas 14, 15, and 16. The working group has renumbered the focus areas from the mandate so that focus area 14 is now 15, 15 is now 16, and 16 is now 14.

Focus area 14 – data sensitivity

Can a better understanding be provided for the spectrum of data sensitivity? That is to say, not only personal sensitivity but also agreements, dual-use pre-prints, IPR, etc., including the researchers' own criteria for how the sensitivity of their data can be understood.

Goal(s):

A concluding article that explores whether a broadly accepted understanding of the concept of data sensitivity can be established among Danish universities—specifically data sensitivity with examples from specific research areas. If this proves not to be possible, an attempt will be made to formulate a set of guiding principles that can serve as a tool to achieve a better understanding of data sensitivity in a research context.

Reporting:

The CISO Forum under Danish Universities is working to calibrate the universities' data classification models. This work is expected to be included in the working group's conclusions. However, members of the CISO Forum are under considerable pressure, which may delay delivery.

The working group has drafted a simple maturity assessment of universities' ability to use the research data management process for risk identification. This draft is expected to undergo further refinement by the CISO Forum before the end of the year.

Beyond calibrating the universities' data classification models, there are ideas on how the URIS¹⁰ guidelines and TRL (Technology Readiness Levels)¹¹ can be used to develop principles for a risk profile for research projects. This is expected to help create the basis for a differentiated risk profile for different aspects of university operations, which would, in turn, support cost-effective governance for research data.

Reccomendation(s):

It is recommended that work in focus area 14 be primarily undertaken by the CISO Forum, and that the CISO Forum be consulted on whether they can take on this task, allowing working group E to act as a stakeholder group instead.

Appendices:

No appendices.

¹⁰ Udvalg om retningslinjer for internationalt forsknings- og innovationssamarbejde / Committee for guidelines for international research and innovation collaboration

¹¹ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/wp/2018-2020/annexes/h2020-wp1820-annex-g-trl_en.pdf

Indsatsområde 15 – Relevant security requirements

What are the security requirements in connection with storage and sharing of data?

Goal(s):

To map which current security requirements apply to the storage and sharing of data at research institutions in Denmark. Subsequently, an assessment will be made of whether there is a gap between these and the applicable/recognised recommendations for security requirements, including whether there is a perceived need for requirements and/or recommendations for additional measures (in the short and long term).

Reporting:

The chair of focus area 15 suggests refocusing the work solely on security requirements for data sharing, excluding storage, as a comprehensive assessment of storage would require considerable effort. The storage aspect could be better handled by the CIO group under the Danish Universities, provided the CIO group determines that the universities' IT-security architecture is sufficiently mature to make such an assessment worthwhile.

This focus area overlaps with focus area 14, and the work on a simple maturity assessment of the universities' ability to use the research data management process for risk identification, as well as there being an overlap with work undertaken by 'Danish Universities' on developing "National guidelines for identifying activities at Universities where unintentional knowledge transfer may affect the interests of the Universities and Denmark". This work can form the basis for further work in defining the governance framework that universities must establish to prevent data from being shared with unauthorised parties.

Reccomendation(s):

It is recommended that focus area 15 concentrates solely on security requirements for data sharing, and that the goal be revised to:

"To identify current security requirements for data sharing at Danish research institutions. Subsequently, the aim is to assess whether a gap exists between these requirements and current/accepted security recommendations, and to determine whether further requirements and/or recommendations for additional measures (short-term and long-term) are needed."

Appendices:

No appendices.

Indsatsområde 16 – approved solutions/services

In light of research groups' needs to work nationally and internationally with sensitive data, which requires strong and flexible governance, elaborate on the national and international solutions/services that can support this need.

Goal(s):

To identify which national and international solutions/services can support the need to work with sensitive data (both nationally and internationally) in a secure manner. For this, experiences from focus areas 14 and 15 are expected to be incorporated.

Reporting:

During group meetings, it was identified that trust in identity verification by collaborating partners is key to the secure sharing of data. Denmark is ahead in this area through MitID, and the rest of the EU is also progressing, supported by relevant directives. In the long term, this means that nation-states will be responsible for identity validation, and trust in an identity will therefore depend on trust in the nation-state issuing that identity. This area is dependent on Working Group B (Establishing FAIR Infrastructure and Long-Term Preservation). It has been identified that, with regard to governance of data access and distribution, a distinction must be made between requirements for solutions where control of data is lost upon sharing, and solutions where data is not shared, but access is granted in a manner that does not relinquish control (such as with Statistics Denmark).

Reccomendation(s):

It is recommended that this area be addressed through closer collaboration with Working Group B (Establishment of FAIR Infrastructure and Long-Term Preservation), and that efforts be made to incorporate knowledge from initiatives such as the European Health Data Space.

Appendices:

No appendices.

9. Working group F – Valuation of Data

Working Group F addresses the FAIR Reference group's focus area 17.

Focus area 17

What criteria for the value (curation) of data and economic models are applied by local, national, and international data storage services to assess the preservation rationale, economics, and sustainability thereof?

Goal(s):

- A framework for working with the value of datasets from the perspective of key stakeholders.
- A summary of the current policies and work regarding the value of data at universities, etc.
- A discussion of the national status for data valuation, including knowledge gained from international initiatives.
- Recommendations for further coordination of the work.
- Recommendations for specific national initiatives.
- Preliminary plan for 2025.

Introduction

Working group F has been tasked with the collection of knowledge on how the value of data is used in the domains covered by the reference group for the implementation of the national FAIR strategy. This working group and its subject were not present in the first mandate period, whereas this initial reporting will focus on establishing a foundation and framework in which to discuss the subject of the value of data in the scopes of the FAIR principles and the Danish landscape of research data management.

Reporting:

The working group had its inaugural meeting on the 19th of December 2023 on Zoom. Within the first month the group lost three members and settled into following configuration that remained for the rest of 2024: representatives from three universities (Copenhagen Business School, Copenhagen University, and Aarhus University), one representative from the Royal Danish Library, one from The Danish National Archives, and one from DeIC. In the autumn, the work group regained a representative from AAU and now has representation from half of the Danish universities.

Over the year, the group met 12 times, three of those were physical meetings at University of Southern Denmark, University of Copenhagen, and Copenhagen Business School. In addition, the group arranged a workshop with invited guests that was held at The Danish National Archives in June. In addition, the chairperson participated in regular meetings between the chairpersons of the other working groups to ensure coordination and for reporting to the chairperson of The Reference Group. The chairperson was also invited to an information sharing meeting with working group C.

Changes in focus area 17

The group suggests the following changes of the definition of focus area 17.

The original text for focus area 17 is (repeated from the beginning of the chapter):

What criteria for the value (curation) of data and economic models are applied by local, national, and international data storage services to assess the preservation rationale, economics, and sustainability thereof?

The group proposes the following new description:

What criteria for a dynamic value of data as it fluctuates through curation and changes in context are applied by local, national, and international organizations to assess the preservation rationale, economics, and sustainability thereof?

We removed economic models as the economic outlook is just one of many equally important models and outlooks. We changed the part with (curation) into a dynamic value of data as it fluctuates through curation and changes in context as curation is something done to data, that changes the value of that data and, as with the economic model, this is just one of the many things affecting the value of a given data set in each but changing context. We removed data storage services as such services in the group's opinion should have no influence on the value of data. A data storage service provides infrastructure and systems that enable the storage, sharing, and processing of the data owned or controlled by legal entities, e.g., individuals or organizations or for which such entities have usage rights.

The action plan for year one

As stated in the Terms of Reference for the working group, an action plan was drawn up and published by the Reference Group¹² with the goals listed in the beginning of this chapter

As has been known for centuries, the first casualty in any engagement is the action plan (paraphrased from Über Strategie¹³) and so it went with this plan.

The work began with an overview of the policies from the eight universities, which quickly revealed that the value of data was not presently being used in data management policies.

Focus then shifted to the first of the goals, i.e., creating a solid foundation upon which to build a national discussion of the value of data. The group has in many venues been met with enthusiasm and interest in these foundational discussions which lead us to trust in the path chosen. The work with the framework is described in detail in the appendix: *Appendix – Working Group F – Framework for the value of research data 2024*. The appendix: *Appendix – Working Group F – Presentation on FAIR working group F – Value of research data 2024* contains a presentation with further details which was used at the above-mentioned workshop at the Danish National Archives and provoked enthusiastic discussions and a plentitude of suggestions, comments and questions for the continued work in the working group.

To support and inform the framework discussions both within the group, with invited guests at the workshop, and in general discussions during the past year, the group will in the coming year perform a rapid literature review¹⁴ for which we draw on assistance from The Royal Danish Library.

The group will follow standard search strategies, but keep in mind the nature of such a review in the context of The Reference Group, i.e., this is not a full-blown research project, but a national coordination effort for which we seek a foundation. As a side product, the group will publish a common and open reference library¹⁵ for all to use.

As the group had very positive experiences regarding productivity, collaboration, and energy in the three in-person meetings during 2024 as compared to regular video meetings, we intend to perform the literature review during a retreat in the beginning of 2025.

The group will then finalise the first version of the framework.

In addition, the group is designing a process for gathering information and knowledge from the universities and other relevant Danish institutions, e.g. the foundations and DeiC. The group will create an interview guide and propose a set of roles for interviewing. This will include researchers, policy makers, and upper

¹² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11082776>

¹³ Moltke, H.K.B. von. 1891. Über strategie. Kriegsgeschichtliche einzelschriften. Mittler. <https://books.google.dk/books?id=s8diewAACAAJ>.

¹⁴ A rapid review is a faster and less comprehensive version of a systematic review, where the research literature is reviewed and analyzed in a shorter time frame using simplified or limited methods. <https://kub.kb.dk/systematiske-reviews>

¹⁵ Zotero Group Library: https://www.zotero.org/groups/5739556/data_value_fair_wg_f_2024_2025

management from the chosen institutions. The design will be finalised in the beginning of 2025 and be implemented later in 2025. The details of this design and arguments for a qualitative study can be found in the appendix: *Appendix – Working Group F – Collection of information on data value 2024*.

To ensure support from and proper use of informants, the working groups of the Reference Group will coordinate initiatives involving outside actors in e.g., common workshops and focus group interviews during the coming year.

Lastly, the first version of the framework and the results from the information and knowledge gathering initiatives will form the basis of the final report of the 2024/25 mandate period including the second version of the framework.

Reccomendation(s):

After this first year of work, the group presents no recommendation for the universities in the implementation of the National Strategy for Data Management based on the FAIR principles.

We do present the following recommendations for The Reference Group:

- A new description of Focus Area 17 as described in this chapter.
- Ensure a coordinated effort between the working groups in employing people from stakeholder organisations and institutions for surveys, focus group interviews, interviews, and workshops.

Appendices:

- Appendix – Working Group F – Framework for the value of research data 2024
- Appendix – Working Group F – Presentation on FAIR working group F – Value of research data 2024
- Appendix – Working Group F – Collection of information on data value 2024

10. Implementing the strategy in an international context

Remit and Terms of Reference for the Reference group 2023-25¹⁶ is framed within a national context, primarily based on the "Report on the National Strategy for Data Management based on FAIR Principles (2022)"¹⁷, which was completed during the previous mandate period. During the current mandated period, the working groups have sought a deeper understanding of the European and global landscape. This is crucial, particularly because a central goal of the FAIR principles is interoperability, achievable only through the use of common standards. Equally important is to optimise our resources by learning from, if not directly adopting, established solutions and by learning from the expertise within the EOSC (European Open Science Cloud) community, which already possesses considerable knowledge in the area of FAIR data management.

[The European Open Science Cloud EU Node](#) was launched on the 21st of October 2024, offering all European researchers access to a range of services/infrastructures, including those for data storage and processing on virtual machines. Researchers receive credits to purchase services, automatically renewed every three months. It will be interesting to observe how the EOSC federation develops with other nodes, including national offerings for data and service access. Currently, EOSC is focused on establishing organisational, governance, and financial models.

Denmark is actively involved in several EOSC initiatives¹⁸ and is exploring the possibility of establishing a Danish or Nordic EOSC-node. Through EOSC projects with Danish participation, we can gain insights into developments in the following areas: FAIR competencies, long-term preservation, data value, PID policies, and security. In the security domain, EOSC is focused on "Trusted Research Environments" through the recently launched EOSC-ENTRUST project. DeIC is participating in this project in collaboration with Danish participants in ESFRI ELIXIR (bioinformatics).

Competencies:

The Skills4EOSC project has established a network of European FAIR data management competence centers to provide researcher support and to promote the FAIR principles. These competence centers serve as recognised points of reference, connecting various stakeholders and promoting standardised FAIR practices. Currently, such competence centers exist in France, Luxembourg, Italy, Greece, North Macedonia, and Slovenia¹⁹. Similar competence centers also exist in Finland and Sweden, although they are not formally part of EOSC. The Skills4EOSC project has developed training materials²⁰ that are publicly available and can be used by the competence centers.

PID Policies:

A recently completed EOSC Task Force: *PID Policy and Implementation*, has published reports on the PID landscape within EOSC²¹ and on various discipline-specific perspectives on PIDs²², while the FAIR-IMPACT

¹⁶ Uddannelses- og Forskningsstyrelsen. (2024). Remit and Terms of Reference for the Reference group for the implementation of the National Strategy for Data Management Based on the FAIR Principles. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10692851>

¹⁷ Hansen Renner, J., Holmstrand, F. K., Rasmussen, M., de Lichtenberg, U. N., Buss, M., Schlichting, T., Larsen, S. K., Hansen, G. J., Pies-Heje, J., Quinones, R., Kaspersen, S. B., Jensen, H., Kruuse, K. K., Vendelboe, K. K., Begtrup, W. J., Burmeister, B. N., Belsø, R., Dalum, M. P., Pica, C., ... Falktoft, A. (2023). Afrapportering vedrørende den Nationale Strategi for Data Management baseret på FAIR Principper (2022). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7575581>

¹⁸ DeIC as EOSC National mandated member via the Ministry of Higher Education and Science, participates in the following EOSC-projects focusing on data management or research: [FAIR-IMPACT](#), [EOSC Entrust](#), [Skills4EOSC](#), [Submerge](#) and participation in [EOSC Task Force FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects](#)

¹⁹ SKILLS4EOSC COMPETENCE CENTRES NETWORK REGISTRY <https://www.skills4eosc.eu/network>

²⁰ SKILLS4EOSC. DELIVERABLES & MILESTONES <https://www.skills4eosc.eu/resources/deliverables-milestones>

²¹ Mapping current PID-related activities in the EOSC context (A landscape analysis of PID activities) DOI10.5281/zenodo.11396767

²² Community-specific (and stakeholder category-specific) perspectives on the EOSC PID architecture and the EOSC PID policy DOI10.5281/zenodo.11396803

project has developed guidelines for creating EOSC-compliant PID policies²³. Several countries have developed national PID policies²⁴, outlining when, how, and which PID-solutions should be used.

Long-Term Preservation and Retention:

Regarding long-term preservation, EOSC has established a Task Force on Long-Term Data Preservation (2021-2024), which has produced two reports²⁵ that strongly emphasise the importance of clear policies, roles, and responsibilities for long-term preservation. A new Task Force, *Long-Term Data Retention (2024-2026)*²⁶, has been formed, focusing on data value and when data should be deleted.

This section presents a selection of EOSC initiatives, but many more exist. This provides an indication of what the EOSC landscape entails and can contribute to our understanding of future directions for FAIR data management in Denmark and internationally.

²³ Guidelines for creating a user tailored EOSC compliant PID Policy formulates 16 guidelines for helping PID Managers to formulate an EOSC compliant PID policy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11354245>

²⁴ NISO. National PID Strategies. <https://www.niso.org/niso-io/2024/08/national-pid-strategies>

²⁵ LTDP Recommendations & Assertions DOI [10.5281/zenodo.10014697](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10014697), LTDP TF Final Report and Recommendations DOI [10.5281/zenodo.10820892](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10820892).

²⁶ EOSC Association. Long-Term Data Retention Task Force. <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/long-term-data-retention-task-force/>

11. Overview of the FAIR Reference group and working groups

This report was prepared by working groups established by the FAIR Reference group, at the mandate of The Ministry of Higher Education and Science.

FAIR Reference group

- John Renner Hansen, University of Copenhagen, DeIC (Chair)
- Annemarie Falktoft, Ministry of Higher Education and Science
- Anne Sofie Fink, DeIC
- Lasse Aistrup Rosendahl, Independent Research Fund Denmark
- Børge Lindberg, Innovation Fund Denmark
- Morten Andreasen, Danish National Research Foundation
- Lene Oddershede, Novo Nordisk Foundation
- Carsten Sørensen, Copenhagen Business School
- Jonas Langeland Pedersen, Universities Denmark
- Kim Brinckmann, University of Copenhagen
- Martin Svensson, University of Southern Denmark
- Søren Broberg Nielsen, Aarhus University
- Bjarke Stoltze Kaspersen, Ministry of Higher Education and Science
- Hanne-Louise Kirkegaard, Ministry of Higher Education and Science
- Tore Burkal Larsen, Independent Research Fund Denmark
- René Belsø, DeIC (Specialist secretarial support)
- Sandra Boerman, DeIC (Specialist secretarial support)

Working group A – Policies, tools and research support for FAIR data management

- Kirsten Krogh Kruuse, Royal Danish Library (Chair)
- Jens Grønbech Hansen, Aarhus University
- Jens Hybschmann, IT University of Copenhagen
- Konstantinos Tsirigos, Technical University of Denmark
- Lars Ove Dragsted, University of Copenhagen
- Lindie Tessmer Andersen, Danish National Archives (until June 2024)
- René, Belsø, DeIC

Working group B – Establishing FAIR infrastructure and long term preservation

- Bo Bai, DeIC (Chair)
- Jonas Rank Møller, University of Copenhagen
- Allan Timmerman, Aarhus University
- Julian Quick, Technical University of Denmark
- Ulla Gro Nielsen, Novo Nordisk Fonden
- Tjerk Heijboer, GEUS
- Asger Væring Larsen, Royal Danish Library
- Hans Henrik Halvbjörn, Danish National Archives
- Jens Begtrup, Danish National Archives
- Nicolaj Pedersen Tanderup, DeIC

Working Group C – Financial plan for FAIR data

- Ulrik Nicolaj de Lichtenberg, Novo Nordisk Foundation (Chair)
- Lise Arleth, University of Copenhagen
- Jakob Sørensen, Aarhus University
- Birger Larsen, Aalborg University
- John Renner Hansen, University of Copenhagen, DeIC
- Tore Burkal Larsen, Independent Research Fund Denmark
- Børge Lindberg, Innovationsfonden
- Morten Andreasen, Danmarks Grundforskningsfond
- Sandra Boerman, DeIC

Working Group D – Plan for structuring and developing FAIR competencies and knowledge

- Mareike Buss, Copenhagen Business School (Chair)
- Haakon Lund, University of Copenhagen
- Sara Marie Westh, Aarhus University
- Evgenios Vlachos, University of Southern Denmark
- Claus Hansen, Aalborg University
- Falco Hüser, Royal Danish Library
- Sacha Zurcher, Royal Danish Library
- Hannah Mihai, DeIC

Working group E – Security aspects of FAIR data collaboration

- Thomas Schlichting, University of Copenhagen (Chair)
- Peter Severin de Fønss, Aarhus University
- Robert Smith, Aalborg University
- Mads Sinkjær Kjærgaard, Roskilde University
- Bjørn Høj Jakobsen, University of Southern Denmark
- Janni Lee Brodersen, University of Southern Denmark
- Lasse Tougaard Friis, Ministry of Higher Education and Science
- Jakob Bech Petersen, DeIC
- Morten Ingvar Falck (Until June 2024)

Working Group F – Valuation of data

- Per Møldrup-Dalum, Aarhus University (Chair)
- Susanne den Boer Beckers, University of Copenhagen
- Søren Friis Hansen, Copenhagen Business School
- Michael Svendsen, Royal Danish Library
- Jens Begtrup, Danish National Archives
- Anne Sofie Fink, DeIC
- Carina Ollerup Christensen, Aalborg University

12. Appendices

All appendices have been uploaded to Zenodo, and can be found in the community: [Danish National Strategy for FAIR implementation 2023-25](#)

- Appendix - Working Group A – Policies, tools, and research support for FAIR data management. Report 2023-2024
- Appendix- Working Group B- Danish data repositories and long-term preservation 2024
- Appendix- Working Group B – Overview of data management plan tools 2024
- Appendix – Working Group F – Framework for the value of research data 2024
- Appendix – Working Group F – Presentation on FAIR working group F – Value of research data 2024
- Appendix – Working Group F – Collection of information on data value 2024